

Search for Potent Anthelmintics—Part XIII

2-(3,5-Substituted Salicylamido/Cinnamido)-4,5-Substituted Thiazoles

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Manuscript received 27 November 1978, revised 28 February 1979; accepted 24 August 1979

Twenty one new 2-(3,5-substituted salicylamido)-4,5-substituted thiazoles and ten 2-(substituted cinnamido)-4,5-substituted thiazoles have been prepared. Eight of them, when screened against *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in rats and *Hymenolepis nana* in mice at doses of 250 mg/kg × 3 and 250 mg/kg × 1 respectively, were found to be inactive.

3,5-SUBSTITUTED salicylamide derivatives like Niclosamide¹, Rafoxamide² and Clixamide³ have recently emerged as a new class of anthelmintics. Some 2-substituted thiazoles⁴⁻⁷ have shown strong anthelmintic efficacy in mice. Some cinnamic acid derivatives^{8,9} have been known to be active against *S. obvelata* and *A. suum*. Keeping this in view the title compounds were synthesised.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

2-(3, 5-Substituted salicylamido)-4, 5-substituted thiazoles (Table 1) :

These were prepared according to the procedure A or B.

Procedure A :

A mixture consisting of 3, 5-substituted salicyloyl chloride^{10,11} (.01 mole), chloroform (30 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (.01 mole) was cooled in ice and an appropriate amino thiazole¹²⁻¹⁴ (.01 mole) gradually added to it. The resulting mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 6 to 8 hr, cooled and filtered. Concentration of the filtrate afforded a solid which was washed successively with NaHCO₃ solution, dil HCl and water. It

TABLE 1—2-(SUBSTITUTED SALICYLAMIDO)-4,5-SUBSTITUTED THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	%Nitrogen	
								Found	Calcd.
1.	Cl	Cl	H	NO ₂	148	50	C ₁₀ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	12.24	12.58
2.*	Cl	Cl	H	Br	115	56	C ₁₀ H ₇ BrClN ₂ SO ₂	7.94	7.60
3.	Cl	Cl	H	Cl	122	48	C ₁₀ H ₇ Cl ₃ N ₂ SO ₂	8.22	8.65
4.	Cl	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	140	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	7.98	7.67
5.	Cl	Cl	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	260	40	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₃ N ₂ SO ₂	6.78	7.01
6.*	Cl	Cl	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	H	214	52	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	7.02	7.35
7.	Cl	Cl	OH	COOC ₂ H ₅	215	58	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	7.06	7.47
8.	Br	Br	H	NO ₂	172	45	C ₁₀ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	9.38	9.93
9.	Br	Br	H	Br	160	48	C ₁₀ H ₆ Br ₃ N ₂ SO ₂	5.82	6.13
10.	Br	Br	H	Cl	145	58	C ₁₀ H ₇ Br ₂ ClN ₂ SO ₂	7.18	6.79
11.*	Br	Br	C ₆ H ₅	H	174	51	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	6.44	6.17
12.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	190	54	C ₁₆ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₂ SO ₂	5.46	5.73
13.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	H	195	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	6.24	5.96
14.	Br	Br	OH	COOC ₂ H ₅	205	52	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	6.28	6.04
15.	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	176	46	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ SO ₂	17.66	18.07
16.	H	NO ₂	H	Br	120	48	C ₁₀ H ₇ BrN ₂ SO ₂	12.55	12.21
17.	H	NO ₂	H	Cl	230	52	C ₁₀ H ₇ ClN ₂ SO ₂	14.46	14.02
18.	H	NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	168	56	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO ₂	11.80	12.31
19.	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	190	42	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ SO ₂	10.75	11.18
20.*	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	H	250	46	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ SO ₂	11.42	11.77
21.*	H	NO ₂	OH	COOC ₂ H ₅	180	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ SO ₂	11.53	11.97

* Screened for anthelmintic activity.

TABLE 2—2-(SUBSTITUTED CINNAMIDO)-4,5-SUBSTITUTED THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Nitrogen	
							Found	Calcd.
1.*	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	203	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO	8.76	9.13
2.*	H	CH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	140	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₂	8.41	8.86
3.*	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	215	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ SO	8.63	8.22
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	CH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	280	56	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ SO ₂	7.68	7.99
5.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	NO ₂	248	60	C ₁₂ H ₉ ClN ₂ SO ₂	13.14	13.57
6.	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₆ H ₅	H	200	68	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ SO	8.58	8.22
7.	<i>o</i> -Cl	H	NO ₂	210	60	C ₁₂ H ₉ ClN ₂ SO ₂	14.10	13.57
8.	<i>o</i> -Cl	CH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	267	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ SO ₂	8.28	7.99
9.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₆ H ₅	H	190	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ SO	11.60	12.04
10.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	H	NO ₂	230	54	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO ₂	17.19	17.61

* Screened for anthelmintic activity.

was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether or ethanol.

Procedure B :

To an ice cold mixture of 3, 5-substituted salicyloyl chloride (.01 mole) and pyridine (30 ml), an appropriate amino thiazole (.01 mole) was added slowly with stirring. The contents were refluxed for 6 hr and excess of solvent distilled off. The residue was poured into ice cold water whereupon a solid separated out. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

2-(Substituted cinnamido)-4,5-substituted thiazoles (Table 2) :

These were prepared analogously from an appropriately substituted cinnamoyl chloride¹⁻⁶ and an amino thiazole by following the procedure B. The compounds were recrystallised from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

Grateful acknowledgement of the authors is due to Prof. S. S. Tewari, Head, Chemistry Deptt., Lucknow University for providing departmental facilities and Dr. Nitya Nand, Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for pharmacological data of the compounds. One of the authors (S.N.M.) is also thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

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